

REPORT:

*A1.1.1: Literature and market research:
definitions, characteristics,
specifications, application and function
of flow control components*

Work package 1

This report was written as part of activity 1.1.1 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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EMPIR

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Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.1.1 M6	Using input from A1.1.2 and the End-user Advisory Board (A5.1.1), HSGIMIT, INESC MN, TUBITAK and BHT will perform a literature and market research in order to compile and classify flow control components (such as reservoirs, valves, chambers, external connectors, tubing). Within this research, the partners will investigate the definitions, characteristics (such as flow range), specifications (such as accuracy), application and function (such as droplet generation) of the components.	HSGIMIT , INESC MN, TUBITAK, BHT

1. Scope

Precise flow rate control is critical for most microfluidic applications. There are a variety of ways to supply a microfluidic chip with a specific volume or flow rate.

The simplest way is to connect a **flow generator**, which can be a syringe **pump** that provides a flow rate independent of the fluidic resistance of the connected chips or a fluid pump such as a piezo-electric pump or a roller pump. However, the latter have the disadvantage of being dependent on the fluidic resistance of the microfluidics chip to which they are connected. To compensate for this dependence, it is usual to connect a flow sensor between the pump and the chip to measure the flow rate and adjust the pump rate if necessary (flow control).

Some systems use a **pressure** differential sensor to control flow (hydrostatic or by pressure generators). The disadvantage of flow control via **hydrostatic pressure** is that the flow rate is highly dependent of the filling level of the inlet reservoir. On the other end, such dependence is eliminated by using a **pressure generator**. But these two systems are dependent on the fluidic resistance of the chip. Again, a way to get around this is to include a flow or pressure sensor or a valve for flow control.

As a last option, one can still deliver a specific volume of liquid in a microfluidic chip with the help of a manual **pipette** or by pressing a **blister**. However, the majority of these generate flow that is not

controllable nor constant due to their manual handling. Only in digital pipettes there is the possibility to control the velocity of fluid deliver.

Examples of flow control components are flow generators, flow measurement control components, and flow accessories as connectors, tubing or reservoirs, that will impose a flow rate in a microfluidic chip. The list of components used for flow control has been structured in sections and subsections as follows:

2. Flow generators

2.1 Pumps

2.1.1 Syringe pumps

2.1.2 Piezo electric pumps

2.1.3 Peristaltic pumps

2.2 Pressure sources/regulators

2.3 Manual dispensers

2.3.1 Pipettes

2.3.2 Blisters

3. Flow measurement/control components

3.1 Sensors

3.2 Flow sensors

3.2.1 Thermal sensors

3.2.2 Differential pressure flow sensors

3.2.3 Coriolis flow sensors

3.3 Pressure sensors

3.4 Other types of flow sensors

3.5 Valves

4. Flow control accessories

This document provides a compilation and classification of flow control components obtained from literature and market research. Within this research, the investigation of definitions, characteristics such as flow range, specifications such as precision and accuracy, application and function such as droplet generation, of the components are addressed in the following sections.

2. Flow Generators

This section presents a literature and market research on flow generators divided in pumps, pressure sources/regulators and manual dispensers.

2.1 Pumps

2.1.1 Syringe pumps

For a precisely adjustable flow rate depending on the geometry of the connected microfluidic chip, a syringe pump is the most used. The syringe pump has an endless screw that adjusts automatically to the syringe coupled to the instrument. Table 1 provides an overview of manufacturers, flow rates, resolution and accuracy of syringe pumps.

Table 1. Examples of manufacturers, volumetric flow rates, resolution and accuracy of syringe pumps in the market

Type	Supplier	Range of volumetric flow rate	Resolution	Accuracy
Nemesys S	Cetoni	0.008 – 0.06 nL/min up to 38 - 300 mL/min <i>dependent on the syringe used</i>	0.0001 mL/h	
Nexus 3000	Nexus	12 pL/min to 500 mL/min	0.0001 mL/h	MPE \pm < 0.35 %, 0.1 % reproducibility
Perfusor Compact S	BBraun	0.16 mL/min - 3.3 mL/min	0.1 mL/h	2%
PerfusorSpace	BBraun	0.16 mL/min - 16.65 mL/min	0.01 mL/h	2%
Fusion	KR Analytical	Min _{0.5} μ L syringe: 0.01 nL/min Max ₆₀ mL syringe: 90 mL/min		1%
Legato 100	Kd Scientific	Min _{0.5} mL syringe: 0.01 nL/min Max ₁₀ mL syringe: 25.99 mL/min Max ₆₀ mL syringe: 88.28 mL/min		0.5%
SK500II	SK Medical	1.6 mL/min - 16 mL/min	0.1 mL/h	2%
NE 1000	New Era	Min ₁ mL syringe: 0.01 μ L/min Max ₆₀ mL syringe: 35 mL/min		1%
PHD 22/2000	Harvard Apparatus	Min _{0.5} mL syringe: 0.01 nL/min Max ₁₄₀ mL syringe: 220.82 mL/min		0.35%

2.1.2 Piezo electric pumps

Piezo-electric (diaphragm) pumps require compact drives that can provide a continuous flow and variable flow rates. Due to the small volumes per pumping cycle, high cycle rates up to the kHz-range are necessary to achieve high flow rates. Table 2 provides an overview of the manufacturers and volumetric flow rates of piezo-electric pumps.

Table 2 Examples of manufacturers and typical volumetric flow rates of piezo-electric pumps

Type	Supplier	Range of volumetric flow rate
LT Series Micropumps (gas only)	TTP Ventus	
MP 6	Bartels	5 - 8000 μ L/min
SDMP302	Takasago	max. 3 ml/min
SDMP306	Takasago	max. 7 ml/min

2.1.3 Peristaltic pumps

Peristaltic pumps have a mechanical trigger causes the liquid within the tube to move by peristaltic action, thus enabling the delivery of liquids. This mechanism can be classified as rotary or linear. Peristaltic pumps deliver a pulsatile flow. Table 3 provides an overview of the manufacturers, flow rates, resolution and accuracy of peristaltic pumps.

Table 3 Examples of manufacturers, volumetric flow rates, resolution and accuracy of peristaltic pumps found in the market

Type	Supplier	Range of volumetric flow rate	Resolution	Accuracy
403U/R1	Watson Marlow	0.66 mL/min - 1060 mL/min		5%
SK600III	SK mMedical	16 mL/min – 33 mL/min	0.1 mL/h	5%
RP-Q1.2N-P20Z-DC3V	Aquatech Co	20 µL/min - 1100 µL/min		
Masterflex Economy Drive	Sartorius	30 µL/min - 4000 µL/min		
CPP-1 pump family	Jobst Technology	0.15 µl/min - 180 µl/min 2 µl/min - 1700 µl/min		

2.2 Pressure sources/regulators

To create flow in a microfluidic chip, one can apply pressure to a sealed fluid-filled reservoir. Pressure sources or proportional pressure control valves are usually used for pressure control. However, this approach has the disadvantage that at a constant set pressure, the flow rate depends on the fluidic resistance. Examples of pressure sources/regulators are presented in table 4.

Table 4 Examples of manufacturers, flow pressure, resolution and accuracy of pressure sources/regulators

Type	Supplier	Range	Resolution	Accuracy
MFCST TM series	Fluigent	0 - 2000 mbar		
OB1	Elveflow	0 - 200 mbar	6.1 µbar	10 µbar
VPPM series	Festo	0 - 2000 mbar		
AF1 200	Elvesys	0 - 200 mbar		
VS-750	Biophysical Tools	0 - 750 mbar		
Mitos Fluika Pump	Blacktrace (Dolomite)	0 - 500 mbar		

2.3 Manual dispensers

2.3.1 Pipettes

Piston pipettes are used to deliver small amounts of liquid. These instruments can be of fixed or variable volume. Digital pipettes are also available, where the fluid delivery can be programmed at constant velocity. Table 5 provides an overview of the manufacturers, flow rates, resolution and accuracy of pipettes.

Table 5 Examples of manufacturers, flow rates, resolution and accuracy of pipettes found in the market

Type	Supplier	Range	Resolution	Accuracy
Fixed	Eppendorf, Gilson, Sartorius, Mettler, Biohit, VWR, Brand, Thermofisher, Socorex	1 mL - 20 mL	NA	According to ISO 8655
Variable	Eppendorf, Gilson, Sartorius, Mettler, Biohit, VWR, Brand, Thermofisher, Socorex,	0.1 mL - 20 mL	Depends on the volume	According to ISO 8655
Digital	Sartorius, Brand, Oxford	0.2 mL - 10 mL	Depends on the volume	According to ISO 8655

2.3.2 Blisters

Many lateral flow assays require the use of a wash buffer, lysis biochemicals, dilutant, fluorescence labels, PCR master mixes etc. The volumes typically range between 5 and 5000 µl. This typically imposes a requirement for a separate buffer bottle and possibly the use of a volumetric or disposable pipette, which can lead to operator error as well as inconvenience and effects on the ability to qualify the flow in the device. One alternative is to design features for onboard storage of chemicals into the system. Integrated unit-dose buffers/reagents can minimize user errors, minimize contamination risks and eases the use. The most simple and reliable form is to have ambient-stable dried reagents in the devices. Alternative options are liquid filled blister packs, pouches or reservoirs. The option to deliver the device with prefilled channels is less often used.

Pouch: a bag of small or moderate size for storing or transporting chemicals; Pouches are flexible and include a base gusset to allow the product to stand unsupported.

Blister: a raised area on the chip that contains a liquid. Liquid filled blisters can be manufactured from multiple layers of metal and polymer films with tuned capabilities on chemical resistivity and moisture barriers. The liquid can be release by applying pressure on top of the blister; the foil on the bottom either breaks due to the overpressure or is pushed against a sharp object, puncturing the foil. Technical challenges in implementing blisters include blister design to fit cartridge and reagent volume specification, air-free blister filling, reproducible blister rupture, controlled reagent release (volume and rate), and bubble free reagent delivery. Blisters used for pills cost typically 0.25-0.5 euro cents. The complexity of blisters compatible with microfluidic devices make them much more expensive.

Ampoule: A hermetically sealed vial made of glass or plastic that contains a liquid.

Reservoir (or tank): rigid can mounted on the surface and filled with reagent.

Frangible seal technology: Enables the controlled release of testing reagents, eliminating the need for complex fluid handling systems. Frangible sealed reservoirs use differential weld strengths that are designed to fail under specific pressures, allowing for a unit-of-use measure to be precisely delivered to a target well or reaction zone. The availability of different materials enables manufacturers to develop custom form factors for a host of media, including powders; latex and magnetic beads; and aqueous, alcohol-based, and organic liquids. The resulting packaging is extremely stable and can be easily integrated into a variety of test platforms.

Potential reliability / performance issues

- Medium loss during shelf life;
- Integrity of reagent during shelf life;
- Water Vapor Transmission Rate and Oxygen Transmission Rate are dependent on the materials used;
- Leakage;
- Material compatibility and stability;
- Release accuracy;
- Ease of use / simple reagent release and dispense;
- Cost;
- Ease of integration to the manufacturing process chain.

Table 6 presents an overview of blisters/reservoirs available in the market.

Table 6 Overview of blisters/reservoirs

Supplier	Minimum Volume (mL)	Maximum Volume (mL)	Type	Comments
Aradigm	50	50	blister	with nozzle holes
Captite	85	1100	reservoir	
Celula	5	1000		integrated reservoirs with snap on lid
Curetis				integrated prefilled reservoirs
Daktari	180	180	blister (developed by ThinXX)	three blisters in a row pitch ~5-6 mm
Elveflow	1500		reservoir	
Hahn-Schickard	50	1000	blister	stickpacks are commercially available
Medical System for Industry	15	45	pouch	
microfluidicsChipShop	500	4500	reservoir	1-3 in a row pitch 18 mm
microfluidicsChipShop	25	1000	blister	
ThinXX	150	5000	blister	
ThinXX			reagent plug (in development)	designed for easy pick & place

3. Flow measurement/control components

3.1 Sensors

3.2 Flow sensors

Flow rate is one of the most difficult parameters to quantify because it cannot be measured by a direct method. However, numerous indirect measurement methods exist, each with their own advantages and disadvantages. Flow measurement principles range from measuring the **pressure drop** across a restriction, **temperature difference**, **fluid velocity** (tracer particles), **phase difference** (acoustic), **frequency**, or **Coriolis** force, as examples.

All these measurement methods require a specific calibration, which depends, for example, on the fluid properties and suitability for a limited measurement range. The following sections give an overview of different market-proven flow sensor principles. Most of the commercially available flow sensors are manufactured in MEMS technology and are therefore more expensive and not necessarily intended for use as consumables, with the exception of Sensirion's sensor.

3.2.1 Thermal sensors

Thermal flow sensors use the thermal properties of liquids like heat capacity to determine the volumetric flow. They can be divided into three types: Hot-wire anemometers, time-of-flight and calorimeters. The most common method is calorimetric, in which a heating element (H1) is positioned between two sensing elements (T1, T2). In this case the heat transfer is dependent on the volume flow rate. The sensor can measure bidirectionally if two temperature sensors T1 and T2 are mounted on either sides of a heater H1. The main drawbacks of this concept are that the flow sensor must be calibrated to the heat capacity of each medium and the sensor heats the fluid during measurement.

3.2.2. Differential pressure flow sensors

There are a number of different flow sensors which work according to the differential pressure method, e.g. Pitot tube, Venturi or orifice plate flow meter. In all cases, the flow velocity is increased by a narrowing of the cross section. This increase leads to a measurable pressure drop in the system, that is proportional to the flow rate. A differential pressure flow meter consists of two main parts: an obstruction or flow resistance that results a pressure drop in the flow path and a transducer before and after to measure the drop.

3.2.3. Coriolis flow sensors

In comparison with thermal sensors which measures volume flow, Coriolis flow sensors are true mass flow sensor. The Coriolis force is an apparent or inertial force that deflects a moving body transverse to its direction of motion when the motion is described relative to a rotating reference system. The main advantage of this flow sensor is the independence between the measured flow rate and the properties of the liquid.

Table 7 presents an overview of sensors used in microfluidic devices to measure flow rate.

Table 7 Examples of flow sensors available in the market and their resolution and accuracy given by the manufacturer

Type	Supplier	Range	Resolution	Accuracy
Thermal flow sensors				
LD20-2600B	Sensirion	0 – 1660 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$		$\pm 0.25\%$ FSO
Microfluidic flow sensor - MFS	Elveflow	1.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ - 5 mL/min	down to 1.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{sec}$	< 5%
μ -FLOW	Bronkhorst	Min: 5 - 100 mg/h Max: 0.1 - 2 g/h		$\pm 2\%$ FSO
LF6000	Siargo	0.5 - 6.0 mL/min (liquid)	better than 20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	$\pm 3\%$ or $\pm 0.05\%$ mL/min , which is greater
Differential pressure flow sensor				
MEMS flow meter	Seyonic	1- 200 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$		0.5%
Coriolis flow sensor				
Mini CORI-FLOW ML120	Bronkhorst	0.05 - 0.5 g/h , Max 200 g/h		$\pm 0.2\%$ FSO

3.3 Pressure sensors

Pressure sensors are widely used in research and industry, such as the automotive industry, process engineering, medical technology or the chemical industry. They differ in their measuring principle, the measuring range, manufacturing costs and their suitability for specific fields of application. A new but steady growing market for the application of pressure sensors is the field of medical technology.

The most common sensor type is the diaphragm-based pressure sensor. Pressure exerted onto one side of the diaphragm results in its deflection, whereby the pressure range depends on the diaphragm geometry and properties. The deflection of the sensing element can be measured by e.g. a piezoelectric, piezoresistive, capacitive or with strain gauges element located on the surface of the diaphragm. Table 8 shows examples of pressure sensors available in the market and their resolution and accuracy given by the manufacturer.

Table 8 Pressure sensors found in the market used for pressure measurements in microfluidic devices

Type	Supplier	Range of pressure	Resolution	Accuracy
Singe-use pressure sensor	PendoTECH	-66 - 200 mbar	14 mbar	$\pm 2\%$ FSO (Full-Scale Output)
SciPres	SciLog	-760 - 4140 mbar	1 mbar	$\pm 0.5\%$ FSO
True Wave	Edwards Lifescience	-66 - 400 mar	1 mbar	$\pm 1.5\%$ FSO
Microfluidic inline pressure sensor - MFP	Elveflow	0 - 16 bar		$\pm 2\%$

3.4. Other types of flow sensors

Ultrasonic flow sensors use sound waves to determine the velocity of a flowing medium such as gas or liquid. Advantages are the absence of moving mechanical parts which reduce maintenance and no pressure loss occur due to narrowing of the cross-section. Two essential measuring principles are used in industrial systems for acoustic flow measurement using ultrasound: the *Ultrasound Doppler Method* and the *Ultrasound Transit Time Method*.

Apart from mechanical technology, there are many non-thermal flow measurement solutions available. Some of them involve tracers, optics, acoustics or electrochemical phenomena, to name a few.

3.5 Valves

Valves generally have a membrane and are actuated by a solenoid, a shape memory alloy (SMA), microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) or are fully integrated in the microfluidics system. They are usually mounted in manifolds.

The market of miniature standalone valves is dominated by **solenoid valves**. Solenoid valves are inherently bulky and need distance between them to prevent interference, at least 5 mm according to one supplier. Most of the miniature valves are designed and used for gases (pneumatic control, medical, processing etc.). This goes especially for **piezo** and **MEMS** valves. The reason is likely technical: the short stroke. For microfluidic applications one needs strokes exceeding about 100 microns (up to 500 μm). Together with **SMA** valves, piezo and MEMS valves have the potential of further miniaturization without increasing significantly the cost. Of these three only SMA valves can offer a pathway towards further miniaturization within the application area of microfluidics. For the others the small actuator stroke is likely a barrier. An advantage of piezo valves (and also MEMS and SMA valves) is their silent operation. The topic of silent operation is especially of interest for near-patient applications with valves frequently operated during a long time. For piezo valves, safety for use in explosion sensitive area is also an advantage.

The large majority of the microfluidic disposables features a relatively simple flow path, without valves. If a valve is needed, designers mostly use integrated passive valves. Due to the cost of standalone valves, they are used in microfluidics generally in the instruments, not in the disposables. Interestingly some options present separated valve and actuator: the valve is fabricated on the disposable and the actuator is integrated in the instrument. In these cases, the top layer of the disposable is a flexible membrane that is pressed by pneumatics or an actuator into the microfluidic channel, blocking the channel. Due to the stroke needed, likely piezo and MEMS valves cannot be used for operating blisters.

Fully integrated valves such as arrays of pneumatically operated integrated microvalves have been around in different versions since 2000. Each of them involves different advantages and drawbacks but they are all based on the same principle: the pressure-driven deformation of a soft material (generally silicone based) that clogs or releases liquid flows into microsystems. The method can be used for both valving and pumping. A major advantage of this concept is that it allows for the combination of valves, tubing, pumps and connectors into a single pre-assembled component, thereby reducing production time and costs associated with purchasing, testing, handling and assembling multiple components. Besides that, it allows to integrate a complex processing in a single chip, thereby

reducing the usage of expensive chemicals. Additional advantages are a reduction of space of internal equipment and elimination of unsightly and unmanageable wiring and tubing.

A disadvantage of Quake valves (silicone based, integrated in the microfluidic chip) is that they require a pressure supply, restricting usage to labs. Having standalone actuators in the instruments is not an alternative as those valves need minimal distances from each other, restricting miniaturization. That might be different for arrays of SMA valves, with the actuator in the instrument and the fluidic part in the disposable. Still, this is likely a niche product.

Valves mounted on a rail, manifold, or microfluidic motherboard are the most common methods to combine valves. Most of the valve suppliers offer such manifolds that can only be used with their own valves which are, as a rule, customer made. Manifolds are seen as offering several advantages compared to just tubing together discrete components, such as fewer leakage points, lower internal volumes, easier assembly into the instrument and higher reliability.

Examples of SMA, MEMS and fully integrated valves can be found in table 10.

Table 9 Examples of valves available for microfluidics flow measurement or control

Type	Supplier	Type
Solenoid valves		
SMLD 300G	Gyger AG	- 50 µL CV<5 %
VHS	Lee	- 50 µL CV<5 %
NV-2-MFF (Diaphragm Isolation Valves)	Takasago	2-way NC, 2-way NO, or 3-way
EXAK Series (Diaphragm Isolation Valves)	Takasago	2-way NC, 2-way NO, or 3-way
2/2 Way Microfluidic Whisper Valve Type 6712	Bürkert	2/2 way normally closed
LVF-MFV-NP-22-NC_2	Elveflow	Controllable Microfluidic 2/3 Port Solenoid Valve
SMA valves		
SMA valve	Actuator Solution	Custom made
Bistable micro valve	Memetis	2/2-way valve
SMV 2/2 NC Active Valve	Bartels	2/2 NC
Fully integrated valves		
Nanoflex valves	Fluidigm	

5 Flow control accessories (tubing, nozzles and connectors)

Typical tube outer dimensions (OD) for side connect devices in microfluidic applications are:

- 1/16" (≈1.6 mm)
- 1/32" (≈0.8 mm)

A specific connector, either of the microfluidic chip or of a nozzle, usually only supports one single specific tube size.

Smaller sized tubes and capillaries can be beneficial for 1.5 mm pitch side connect applications. Preferred tube outer diameters are:

- 0.5 mm (usually between 0.44-0.53 mm)
- 0.36 mm (usually between 0.35-0.38 mm)

Table 10 Indicative overview of connectors used in microfluidics

Type	Chips		Pumps				Other				Comments
	Glass	Polymer	Pressure regulated	Peristaltic	Membrane	Syringe	Flow sensor	Other sensors	Valves	Cell cultures / Organ on	
Hose		(x)			x				x	x	
(mini)Luer		x	x			x		x		x	Mostly Luer
Glued	(x)										
1/4-28, etc.			x			x	x	x	x	x	Mostly 1/4-28
Clamped	x										
Manifold or docking station	x								x	(x)	
Other			(x)			(x)					company unique, push in etc.
None				x						x	

x: often used; (x) used now and then

Materials

A wide range of materials is available for the same inner diameter (ID) / OD combination (Table 11). The material is selected according to the nature of the reagents flowing through the tubing. Chemical and biological compatibility of the tubing material is important for the correct implementation of the microfluidic system

Some of the most common microfluidic tubing materials include:

- PEEK (Polyetheretherketone): Biocompatible, chemically inert to most commonly used solvents, low non-specific adsorption. PEEK tubing is flexible, has a very smooth internal surface and is easily cut to required lengths. For low and high-pressure applications. Very small internal diameters available.

- PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene, equivalent to the Teflon®) brand name: Chemically inert to most commonly used solvents, non-toxic, non-porous, excellent stress resistance. Flexible and clear. Mostly for low-pressure applications.
- FEP (Fluorinated ethylene-propylene): Same family as PTFE. Chemically inert to most commonly used solvents and biocompatible. Flexible and clear. Mostly for low-pressure applications.
- ETFE (Ethylene tetrafluoroethylene): Same family as PTFE and FEP but more rigid and better-suited to higher pressure applications.
- Fused silica (high-purity glass): Mainly for capillary tubing, available with outer diameters smaller than 1/32" (360 µm OD, 510 µm OD...). NB: this type of tubing must be cut using ceramic cutters to get clean inlets and outlets.

Table 11 Tubbing used in microfluidics. ID is the tube inner diameter and OD is the tube outer diameter

COMPANY	CONNECTOR TYPE	MATERIAL	TUBBING	
			ID (mm)	OD (mm)
Aline	hose barb	Silicone	-	1/16" or 1.6 mm
Cellix ^{*1}		PTFE ⁶	1	1/16" or 1.6 mm
Cellix ^{*2}	connecting needles ID 0.3 mm; OD 0.5144 mm	Tygon (PVC)	0.439	2.268
Cetoni ^{*3}	fittings with 1/4-28 UNF threads	-	-	1.6
CorSolutions		FEP ^{*5}	-	1.6
		PEEK ^{*7}	-	0.8
Cytosurge		Silicone	1	4
		Tygon (PVC ^{*8})	0.25	-
Diagnostic Biosensors	Luer lock	-	-	-
Dolomite	clamped: Dolomite connectors	PTFE ⁶	0.5; 0.8	1.6
		PTFE ⁶	0.5; 0.8	1.6
		FEP ^{*5}	0.25; 0.1; 0.5; 0.8	1.6
		FEP ^{*5}	0.1; 0.25	0.8
		PEEK ^{*7}	0.25	0.8
flowjem	1/16 threaded connectors	-	-	-
Fluigent ^{*4}	Luer	PEEK ^{*7}	0.125; 0.25; 0.375; 0.5	1.6
		FEP ^{*5}	0.25; 0.5	1.6
		-	0.25; 0.5; 0.9	0.8
		Fused Silicon	0.02	0.36
Gesim	barbed adapter for tube 1/8" A100-086	-	-	-
	barbed adapter for tube 1/16" A100-111	-	1.6	-
	tube flanged on both ends, 300 mm A072-072	-	1.6	-
IBIDI	Luer	Silicone	-	-
Jobst Technologies	0.15mm ID tube termination	-	-	-
Kirkstall		Silicone	-	-
Labsmith	Luer	PEEK ^{*7}	-	1.6
			0.25	0.8
			-	0.36
		Fused Silicon	-	0.36
	Mirluer	Silicone	1/16"	1/8

Table 12 Tubbing used in microfluidics (cont.)

COMPANY	CONNECTOR TYPE	MATERIAL	TUBBING	
			ID (mm)	OD (mm)
microfluidicsChipShop	(mini) Luer	PTFE ^{*5}	0.5; 0.5	1
		PEEK ^{*7}	0.2	1/32" or 0.8 mm
		Silicone	0.76	1.65
		Silicone	0.5	2.5
Microflow CVO	Inlet/outlet ports: 1/8" type 316SS, mixer body: 316SS	PEEK ^{*7} ; EFTE ^{*8} ; 316 SS ^{*10}	0.055"	1/8"; 1/16"
Micronit	flat-bottom or flat bottom nuts and ferrules	-	0.25	1.6
		Teflon (not specified); PEEK ^{*7} ; SS ^{*9}	0.25	1.6
		Fused Silicon	0.15	0.375
Microplumbers	six fluid ports fit microfluidic device with inlets 1 mm diameter or smaller. Fluid ports are 6.35 mm apart Flat-bottom fittings	-	-	-
	Micrux	1/4 - 28	-	-
Norgren Kloen	mounting threads #10-32, ¼-28 or M-6 Standard	PEEK ^{*7} ; SS ^{*10}	-	1/16" or 1.6 mm
Ricell	barbed: 1.0 mm ID; 2+ mm OD	Silicone	-	-
Sigma Aldrich	flatbottom threaded port 1/4" - 28; fittings PEEK	-	-	-
Thinxxs	(mini) Luer	Silicone	1	3
		Tygon (PVC ^{*8})	1.6	3.2
Translume	nanoport	-	-	-

*1 tubings for KIMA pump or EVO nanopump

*2 tubings for EVO nanopump

*3 10 fittings with ¼-28UNF threads for tubes with 1.6 mm outer diameter (suitable o-rings are included).

*4 The standard sizes for Fluigent products are 1/32" and 1/16"

*5 fluorinated ethylene propylene

*6 polytetrafluoroethylene

*7 polyether ether ketone

*8 polyvinyl chloride

*9 ethylene-tetrafluoroethylene

*10 stainless steel

References

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